

Flame synthesis of binary aluminate glass microspheres

Jana Valúchová^{1,2}, Anna Prnová^{1,2}, Milan Parchovianský², Peter Švančárek^{1,2}, Dušan Galusek^{1,2}

¹Join Glass Centre of the IIC SAS, TnUAD, FChPT STU, Študentská 2, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia
(E-mail: jana.valuchova@tnuni.sk)

²FunGlass, A. Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentská 2, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia

ABSTRACT

The aim of this work is preparation and study of properties $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Y}_2\text{O}_3$ glass microspheres. For these glasses excellent mechanical and optical properties comparable to that of single crystal sapphire are expected. Because Al_2O_3 is not a typical glass-former, preparation of these glasses in bulk is very difficult due to high crystallization rates and high melting temperatures, and require therefore high temperatures and high cooling rates. Yttrium aluminate glasses with eutectic composition AY-E (76.8 mol. % Al_2O_3) were prepared in the form of glass microspheres by flame synthesis. The highly homogenous starting powders for flame synthesis were prepared by sol-gel (Pechini) method using corresponding nitrates as starting materials. The basic characterisation of prepared glass microparticles was carried out by XRD, OM and SEM. Two exothermic peaks with maxima at 942 and 1006°C were observed in DSC record. The high temperature X-ray powder diffraction measurements (HT XRD) were carried out in the temperature interval 750 -1450°C with the step of 5°C and the temperature dependence of phase composition was determined. The crystallisation of YAG (yttrium-aluminate garnet) phase was observed in relatively broad temperature interval 900-1200°C, with the steep increase of the YAG phase content between 900 and 950°C, followed by slower increase between 1100 and 1300 °C. The crystallisation of $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ phase follows at temperatures > 1300°C. Preliminary experiments with hot-pressing of the microspheres have been carried out, and the results are reported.

Keywords: yttrium-aluminate glasses, YAG, SEM, DSC, HT XRD

Fig.1 SEM micrographs of YA-E microspheres prepared by flame synthesis. The particles with morphological features (facets) suggesting their polycrystalline nature are marked by arrows.

Acknowledgment:

This paper is a part of dissemination activities of project [FunGlass](#).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739566.

The financial support of this work by the projects APVV 0014-15, VEGA 1/0527/18, VEGA 2/0026/17 is gratefully acknowledged.